

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D5.2

**Beta version of advanced autonomous
functionalities for ground robots and crawlers**

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AMCL	Active Monte Carlo Localization (algorithm)
BIKE	Magnetic pipe inspection robot (robot)
CAD	Computer aided design
CART	Tunnel inspection robot (robot)
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
ETHZ	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zurich (Partner)
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system a general term describing any satellite constellation that provides positioning, navigation, and timing service
ICP	Iterative Closest Point (family of algorithms for point cloud registration)
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit (sensor)
LIDAR	Light detection and ranging (sensor)
LIO SAM	LiDAR-Inertial SLAM library (software)
MPC	Model Predictive Control
OCS2	Control library (software)
PID	Proportional–Integral–Derivative controller: A widely used control loop mechanism.
RBNK	Robotnik Automation S.L.L. (Partner)
RGBD	Optical camera (RGB) plus depth (D) sensing (sensor)
RISING	Refinery inspection robot (robot)
ROS	Robot operating system
ROVIOLI	VI-based localization library (software)
OMPL	Open Motion Planning Library
SBPL	Search-based Planning Library (software)
SDF	Signed Distance Field
SINTEF	Stiftelsen for industriell og teknisk forskning (Partner)
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (functionality)
TEB	Time Elastic Band (algorithm)
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle
VI	Visual-Inertial (sensing functionality based on inertial sensors and camera)
WTR	Waygate Technologies Robotics (Partner)

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The main purpose of this document is to present the beta version of the algorithms developed with respect to dexterous manipulation, advanced perception and intelligent navigation for autonomous inspection and maintenance for ground robots and crawlers.

1.2 Scope of the document

This deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within tasks T5.2 (“Dexterous manipulation from ground vehicles”) and T5.4 (“Perception and intelligent navigation for ground robots and crawlers”) during their first period.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows:

- Section 1 specifies the purpose, scope and structure of the document.
- Section 2 describes the architecture and algorithmic modules developed to detect and manipulate of valve’s hand wheel assets. This section is specific to the RISING ground manipulator use case and summarizes the work performed in task 5.2.
- Section 3 addresses the advanced perception and autonomous navigation modules as developed in T5.4. The ground robotic vehicles have different morphology and are equipped with different sensors and placement layouts, making the implementation robot specific. Each subsection recap the sensing capability of the platform and describes the specific implementation for each ground robot.
- Finally, Section 4 presents some conclusions and future work on the described tasks.

2. Algorithms for Dexterous Manipulation

The RISING platform is the sole ground robot equipped with a manipulator and thus capable of complex manipulation tasks (see deliverable D4.1 for more details). This section introduces the framework and describes the modules deployed on the RISING platform for the autonomous perception and manipulation task as per T5.2. The manipulator consists of a skid-steered mobile base and a 7-DoFs Kinova Gen3 arm. The base is additionally equipped with a pair of flippers in the front and the back. Each pair of flippers can be independently controlled to change the base height and attitude. The 7 DoF is equipped with a wrist mounted 6-axis Force Torque sensor, which provides haptic feedback during interaction with the environment. A 2-finger Robotiq gripper is mounted on the sensor.

Figure 1. Laboratory setup with Kinova arm and 2-finger Robotiq gripper

2.1 High level overview and architecture

The valve manipulation problem requires first perceiving the 3D pose of the valve. Once the 3D pose of the valve has been successfully extracted from the scene, a fixed grasp strategy is deployed according to the relative position between the manipulation and the asset. This is an important step as the manipulator has limited a workspace. After a successful grasp, a manipulation plan is generated. In a simple use case, this could be an arc whose width is a function of the desired change (e.g., opening or closing the valve). Once the plan is generated, this is tracked by an arm-level controller. The deployed hierarchical control method consists of an outer admittance loop followed by a kinematic MPC solver that computes desired joint angles, and then tracked by a pure PID

Figure 2. The high-level system architecture for autonomous manipulation of a handwheel valve. Note that an external automaton handles the switch between grasp and end effector planning.

2.2 Perception for valve manipulation

We assume that an approximate knowledge of the valve location in a previously generated map is available. The navigation pipeline is then in charge of bringing the valve in the field of view of the manipulator. The ZED mini stereo camera mounted at the end effector (eye-in-hand) is then used to provide the visual input for the detection algorithm. In particular, we deploy a combination of a learning method and more traditional template matching for object detection and registration. In the first step, the RGB image is passed through a deep CNN, which outputs valve keypoints. Keypoints have emerged as an alternative object representation in the field of autonomous manipulation. 3D keypoints are interesting points with semantic meaning. An intuitive example could be the center point on the bottom of a cup for leaning and its top for pouring. We identify the valve's keypoints as the intersection points between the valve handwheel and the ribs that connect it to the shaft. We developed an autonomous data collection pipeline that provides labeled training data quickly and with little user intervention. This allows us to collect a rich dataset under various lighting conditions and different valve models. Furthermore, the use of keypoints better generalizes under intra-category variations (e.g., various handwheel shape and visual appearance). The keypoints are predicted for each camera in the stereo setup and triangulated. Once the keypoints pose is known, the valve 3D model, which is also available beforehand, is used to fit a 3D bounding box and estimate an initial pose guess for the following pose registration routine. Note that this step adds redundancy to the perception pipeline, as in the case of good prediction quality, the output from the learning-based detector already contains enough information for manipulation. The input of the object registration is

the point cloud of the object, which is obtained by cropping the original point cloud with the detected bounding box, and a pose guess. ICP is then performed against the known valve model to refine the valve pose.

Figure 3. On the left we depict the valve keypoints with orange dots. The bounding box is also visualized. On the right, the valve 3D model is matched against the point cloud to improve its pose estimate.

2.3 Admittance and Model based control of Ground Manipulator

This manipulation task requires interaction with a stiff environment under imperfect sensing and state estimate (valve and robot pose). Therefore, we need a reactive control method that is able to incorporate the haptic feedback. On the other hand, we would like to leverage the arm redundancy. In order to achieve these requirements, we deploy an admittance feedback control strategy. At the outer loop, the end effector position reference is received. This could come from the grasp or manipulation planner. The plan consists of an ordered list of timed end effector waypoints. The outer loop implements a cartesian impedance scheme. The desired behavior can be tuned by changing its P gains. The impedance behavior is obtained according to the equation:

$$\delta \mathbf{x} = K_p(\mathbf{F}^* - \mathbf{F})$$

The haptic feedback has the effect of translating the end effector desired path such that the arm has the required compliance during interaction. On the other hand, one could actively estimate the viscous and static friction and intentionally apply a non-zero wrench to overcome the valve resistance to turning. We keep this extension for future work. The modified path is then tracked by a kinematic Model Predictive Controller (MPC). We adopted MPC as a more robust, optimization-based alternative to Inverse Kinematics algorithms. In fact, the optimization can take joint constraints into consideration and naturally does not suffer from the bad conditioning in singular arm configurations. For this module, we use the open source library OCS2 (<https://bitbucket.org/leggedrobotics/ocs2/src/master/>).

Figure 4. The control architecture consists of an outer admittance loop followed by an MPC-based motion controller. This structure guarantees satisfactory disturbance rejection during free motion and the desired compliant behavior during interaction.

2.4 Grasp planning

Once the valve pose is known, a fixed grasp can be computed. Note that one can decide among multiple grasping strategies. For instance, if the gripper is wide enough and the valve shaft has a sufficiently small diameter, the gripper could be used to grasp the shaft and manipulate the valve via only the last joint. While this seems the easier solution, it does not cope with the actuation limit of the arm. In fact, the torque provided by a single joint could be insufficient to win the resistance of the valve. Secondly, one could try a “frontal grasp” where the gripper grasps the handwheel with a direction normal to the wheel plane. This solution has the disadvantage that perceiving the holes (spaces between ribs) is also required to avoid hard collisions. We find that a “lateral grasp” is the safest solution as it generalizes well to all valve types. In this case, the gripper approaches the hand wheel radially, in the handwheel plane. Furthermore, the “lateral” grasp has the non-obvious advantage that the gripper can approach the valve at its maximum opening width. This strategy helps to cope with uncertainty in the pose estimation as a wide-open gripper has less chance to collide with the valve if its pose was not correctly estimated. This strategy would not be necessarily feasible for the “frontal” grasp as, depending on the valve shape, because of the potential collision with the radial ribs. It is important to notice that if the manipulator would be position-controlled, closing the gripper around the handwheel in the presence of uncertainty would lead to almost certain failure. In fact, the gripper would force the arm in a different position up to reaching the actuation torque limits. Instead, the outer admittance loop, and low-level torque control make the arm compliant to external forces and drive it autonomously to the ideal grasping configuration. Once the gripper is in a stable grasp configuration, the proprioceptive sensing (joint encoders) could be used to further improve the valve pose estimate. This is currently not implemented and will be further investigated in the future.

3. Perception and Intelligent Navigation

This section introduces the hardware concepts and autonomous functionalities of the ground-based platforms. For each of the three use cases (refinery, pipe, tunnel), we present the hardware, Localization and Mapping, Path planning and trajectory control methods. While some components are similar across all applications, the drastically different environments necessitate specific solutions for each use-case.

3.1 RISING

RISING is a mobile manipulator specially designed for inspection and intervention. The concept aims for a high mobility, robust, modular, easily transportable and easy to deploy robot platform.

The robot is expected to perform routinary surveillance around the refinery in order to identify possible threats and provide situational awareness. For that purpose, the robot will be carrying a set of cameras, including a thermal one together with a PTU unit, but also a 3D laser scanner or even a gas sensor. RGBD cameras and IMU's will be dedicated to improving the GNSS denied navigation in this context.

Apart from that, RISING robot will be carrying a manipulator, making possible different tasks requiring dexterous manipulation, such as actuating levers.

Figure 5. The RISING platform is equipped with a robotic manipulator and visual and range sensors for the inspection and manipulation of elements in a refinery environment.

3.1.1 Localization and Mapping

We employ a Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) framework for environmental modelling and perception as illustrated in Figure 6. As input, we consider a subset of sensor data, i.e., 3D LiDAR, RGB camera, pose-camera, IMU, and wheel encoders. The environmental representation is in the form of 3D point clouds, which lend themselves naturally to the application as it makes it possible to directly integrate readily available point cloud data, e.g., captured from Terrestrial Laser Scanners. The core component of the pipeline is then a framework for state estimation and mapping. The state estimation component consists of different odometry / sensory inputs and receives regular

updates from the low frequency mapping step, integrating new observations into the point-cloud-based map. In our current implementation, we only consider LiDAR data input in the mapping and low frequency state estimation update step, all other sensors are currently only used for state estimation. We build on the library libpointmatcher (<https://github.com/ethz-asl/libpointmatcher>) for LiDAR data.

For the pose estimation step, we can employ different estimation schemes. The most basic one is the direct use of pose measurements from a dedicated sensor and coupling with libpointmatcher (naïve estimator). Another implemented method is a sliding window estimation fusing multiple estimations, in our current implementation, LiDAR, IMU, and wheel encoders, based on the confusion framework (<https://bitbucket.org/tsandy/confusion>).

The mapping step fuses the Maximum a-Posteriori estimate of aligning consecutive LiDAR scans into a larger point cloud map and applying optional filtering steps (e.g., density filtering and feature augmentation for surface normal estimation). Optionally, a pre-recorded map in the form of a point cloud is loaded into the mapper. It is then also possible to switch to a pure localization mode, i.e., the map will not be extended with further data. This is an extension of libpointmatcher (https://github.com/ethz-asl/ethzasl_icp_mapping).

In the future, we will improve the mapping backend with more versatile methods, incorporating further sensor modalities and allowing batch optimization of entire maps, compared to the current greedy scheme. Here, we currently investigate the use of maplab (<https://github.com/ethz-asl/maplab>), which is originally designed for visual-inertial (VI) mapping and a pose-graph back-end for global map optimization. In the next step, we will extend this framework to also register constraints from further sensors, such as pose sensors, and LiDARs. Another optimization is the support of further map representations, such as Signed Distance Fields (SDF) which have the advantage to capture free-space, relevant for navigation.

Figure 6. The SLAM architecture consists of 4 main components. (1) The sensor inputs which of IMU, Pose sensor and 3D LiDAR are already implemented. (2) The state estimator where currently 2 versions are implemented: a sliding

window estimator, and a naïve estimator. (3) The mapper that either iteratively estimates the map from consecutive observations or performs a batch estimation, i.e. a global calculation of the map using a full mission data. (4) The map output in the form of 3D point cloud or SDF map.

Initialization of the localization requires a global estimate. This can be achieved through various measures, e.g., GPS initialization, or global localization in the map. In the current implementation, an approximate initialization is given manually, but automatic global localization is scheduled to be available in the next system iteration. The relevant changes on the current system are the implementation of absolute measurement constraints in the state estimation (already available) and the creation of absolute pose measurements. This is straight-forward in the case of GPS measurements. It is further possible to implement advanced algorithmic methods that perform global localization based on environmental features to also address GPS-denied regions, e.g. Segmap (<https://github.com/ethz-asl/segmap>), but currently this is not planned.

3.1.2 Motion Planning

In order to achieve the defined goal location, we use a global planner based on the OMPL library (<https://ompl.kavrakilab.org/>). The global planner uses a 2d slice of the current map to obtain a 2d Cost Map for planning and obstacle avoidance. The global path is then tracked by a local planner that takes into account the kinematic constraints of the base. In particular, we use the Timed Elastic Band (TEB) local planner. Timed Elastic Band locally optimizes the robot's trajectory with respect to trajectory execution time, separation from obstacles and compliance with kinodynamic constraints at runtime. The planning module is implemented using the standard ROS MoveBase interfaces and message types.

3.1.3 Motion Control

The local plan generated by the TEB planner is tracked by a Model-based Predictive Controller (MPC). The controller uses a simplified 2d kinematic model of the skid steer robot to compute the optimal twist command in a receding horizon fashion. For this module, we use the open source library OCS2 (<https://bitbucket.org/leggedrobotics/ocs2/src/master/>). MPC allows taking into account system velocity constraints and can frequently replan for new incoming base trajectories. Furthermore, MPC can effectively use a timed trajectory where kinematic constraints, such as velocity in between waypoints, are also fulfilled.

Figure 7. The motion planning consists of a cascaded architecture with global planning at the top. The ability to plan and avoid obstacles is tightly coupled to the quality of the cost map and how quickly it changes in a dynamic environment.

3.2 BIKE

The BIKE robot is a magnetic crawler moving on metal surfaces inside pressure vessels and other similar confined spaces. The currently used system is fully controlled by a human pilot, using a joystick attached to the control computer, which communicates to the vehicle over a low latency Ethernet connection (Ethernet over copper). The operator uses visual feedback from the integrated navigation cameras and 3D pose feedback from a localization system to control the robot. The control computer converts the joystick input (speed and steering) to speed references for each of the four wheels. The motor controllers on-board the robot receive the speed reference for the wheels through a dedicated message system over the Ethernet link. The controllers use high-resolution encoders on the motor shafts in local PID control loops to control the speed of each wheel.

Figure 8. BIKE platform with 2D scanning LIDAR for localization in 3D environment.

Figure 9. BIKE platform signal diagram.

The autonomous version to be developed within the PILOTING project will work on the same hardware architecture. The control computer has access to streaming data from the onboard motor controllers, providing wheel speeds, steering angles and other relevant vehicle status registers in a 2 kHz update loop. The output from the path-following module will be converted to a joystick reference value by a new high-level controller and used in the same way as when in manual control.

3.2.1 Localization and Mapping

The BIKE platform uses a pre-existing model of the environment in the form of a mesh. The operator will generate such a model using dedicated modeling software or any CAD system. The model is generated based on available drawings of the as-built of asset or other data, such as 3D scans or photogrammetric reconstruction performed prior to the mission.

Figure 10. Environment Mesh Model Reconstruction of cylindrical environment from scanned pointclouds (created by 2D LIDAR on tilting actuator arm).

The localization method is closely related to a Particle Filter approach (also called a Monte Carlo Method). The sensors used by the robot to feed the filter are: Wheel Encoders, IMU and a 2D scanning LIDAR. The output of the filter is the most likely robot pose.

Figure 11. BIKE localization by environment model and 2D scanning LIDAR.

With the existing environment model, it is already possible to plan and execute paths with the robot. In practice, however, some form of obstacle detection is required for autonomous operation. The localization system can fail due to errors in the environment model (i.e. wrong dimensions etc.). The environment can contain unmodeled or wrongly modeled elements such as structures not shown in drawings or not shown with precise dimensions. Moreover, there might be dynamic elements such as the umbilical cable of the robot, deployment tools or other components used in the process of opening the asset and rendering it safe for access. For these reasons, the PILOTING BIKE will be equipped with a form of obstacle detection. The exact hardware implementation is not yet decided on. Option one is to use the BIKE actuator arm and move the scanning LIDAR to the actuator, allowing for tilting the scanning plane by about 110° . This configuration would allow the acquisition of point

cloud data of the critical vicinity of the robot. It is not very suitable to generate entire scans of the environment though. Therefore a second option of rotating the LIDAR by full 180° on dedicated hardware will be explored. This approach would allow for environment scans missing only a small portion of space where the robot creates a shadow. The obstacle detection process will work in the same way for any of the two hardware solutions.

Figure 12. 2D LIDAR on moving actuator.

Figure 13. BIKE signal diagram for Arm-Actuator option.

Figure 14. 2D LIDAR on direct drive rotating axis.

Figure 15. BIKE signal diagram for rotating 2D LIDAR option.

During robot operation, the LIDAR will continuously produce point cloud data. The data is sent to the control computer and transformed to the global frame of reference. In this process, also subsampling will be performed. In the global frame, two processes will be used for obstacle detection. The fast process will operate on points in the critical area only and simply calculate the distance for any point to the environment model and raise an alarm in case it exceeds a critical threshold. In case of an alarm, the robot will stop and perform a slow, high-resolution scan of the area.

The resulting point cloud will be analyzed by the slow process. The slow process will register the point cloud with the environment model and verify if the transformation is within the acceptable range. If it is not in the acceptable range, the localization system may have failed and an alarm will

be raised for the operator to resolve the problem (i.e., by replacing the robot in the environment manually or by investigating the cause of the problem). If the transformation is close enough to identify, the slow process will perform a different calculation from the point cloud to the environment model and classify the points which exceed a distance threshold as obstacle points. The obstacle points will be grouped into one or more bounding boxes to be reported to the mission control system. The bounding boxes (or alternatively meshes of the obstacle points) will be added to the current environment model. Then the path planner will be started over to generate a new feasible path, avoiding the detected obstacle(s).

3.2.2 Motion Planning

The BIKE platform is able to transition over certain types of obstacles (like concave or convex 90° corners). However, this process is rather delicate and depends on many variables, such as curvature of the involved surfaces and surface condition. It also requires very good alignment of the robot with the corner to transition over (or through). It is currently not the goal to automate these transitions.

For mission planning, the environment will be segmented into elements with autonomous path execution and transition regions. The software makes a heuristic-based analysis of the environment model and shows the mission planner how to segment the asset model. The result is a mission file for each segment, with start and end poses corresponding with the transition points. Once the robot finishes a mission, it will be ready for the human pilot to control it over the corner obstacle. In typical pressure vessels, the only such point is the transition from the deployment flange (manway) into the vessel. In some assets also a transition into a connected vessel or into a sump might occur.

Planning feasible paths for a surface adhering magnetic crawler robot such as the BIKE is a special task. The approach followed for this project is an A* search over a set of admissible voxels under the assumption that all neighboring voxels can be reached. This kind of search is very fast and could potentially be executed continuously. However, the resulting path is not necessarily feasible for the robot and the generation of the admissible set of voxels is computationally more expensive.

Figure 16. Admissible set of voxels for a simple cylindrical surface.

The generation of the admissible set of voxels is only done once per environment model (as long as it remains unchanged). For any path (set of connected admissible voxels), a feasibility check is performed (by moving a simulated robot along the path and checking for collisions). If the path is not feasible at one particular voxel, the voxel will be removed from the admissible set and the A* search started again. This process returns a sequence of voxels (later called milestones) which can be followed by the robot.

Figure 17. A* shortest surface-following path on admissible set of voxels.

3.2.3 Motion Control

Vehicle Control by Local Navigation Functions

The BIKE robot essentially is subject to car-like non-holonomic constraints when moving over the surfaces. Due to the slow speed of the crawler, the only dynamics to be considered is the achievable steering speed.

The control model only considers a 2D situation as it results from projecting the path to the current tangent plane the robot is located on.

Robot Control Model

Pose: $\{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{q}\}$ $\mathbf{x} = [x, y, z]$, \mathbf{q} : quaternion $\rightarrow \mathbf{v}_{fwd}$

Motion State: $\{\mathbf{v}, \varphi\}$ \mathbf{v} : forward velocity m/s, φ : steering angle

Pose update:

- a) Translate: $x_{k+1} = x_k + \mathbf{v} \cdot \Delta T \cdot \mathbf{v}_{fwd}$
- b) Rotate:
 - 1) $d_q = \text{quat.about_axis}(\Delta\theta, [0,0,1])$ - quaternion for rotation around surface normal
 - 2) $q_{k11} = \text{quat.mul}(q, d_q)$ - update quaternion

A common method for controlling non-holonomic vehicles towards a target pose is the use of dipole-field navigation functions. These functions basically provide a reference heading vector to any point

in space. The vehicle control merely needs to orient the vehicle along the field lines and will automatically steer towards the target pose. The advantage of this method, as compared to generating a subsampled path and using a path controller, is the simplicity of the control and the tolerance to deviations in the dynamic vehicle model.

Figure 18: 2D Navigation Field guiding a vehicle towards the origin (black arrow=heading, red arrow = local path curvature)

Controller

The orientation controller operates on the heading error and the path curvature error and controls the steering angle reference as well as the speed reference. The path curvature error is the difference between the local navigation field line curvature and the path curvature currently achieved by the robot steering angle. For controlling the robot, the navigation field curvature is converted into an equivalent steering angle.

Heading Error:

\mathbf{v}_{path} = Gradient of Potential Field

$$\theta_e = \arccos\left(\frac{\mathbf{v}_{fwd} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{path}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{fwd}\| \|\mathbf{v}_{path}\|}\right) \text{sign}(\mathbf{v}_{fwd} \times \mathbf{v}_{path})$$

Curvature Error:

k = curvature of navigation field

$$R = \frac{1}{\|k\|}$$

L = separation distance robot rear axle to front axle

$$\varphi_{path} = \arctan\left(\frac{L}{R}\right) \text{sign}(k)$$

$$\varphi_e = \varphi_{path} - \varphi_{robot}$$

Heading Controller:

$$\varphi_{ref} = K_1 \theta_e + K_2 \varphi_e$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{ref} = f(\varphi, \varphi_e, K_3)$$

Where the function $f(\varphi, \varphi_e, K_3)$ is a mapping of the steering angle and the curvature error to a speed scaler range of $[-1,1]$. The mapping a stabilizing tuning parameter which is chosen such that the robot moves slow enough when a sharp turn is needed, or if a large correction of the steering angle is required. It will be tuned during path following performance evaluation experiments.

For the BIKE control, each voxel will be converted into a milestone consisting of a target pose and a type. The type will indicate if precise approach is required (iterating forward backward or perform spot turns if needed) or if passing by at some tolerance is allowed. The milestone type will also determine if the robot should stop there or not. A navigation function will be used to guide the BIKE towards each milestone.

3.3 CART

The CART is an autonomous ground vehicle that resembles an advanced golf cart with a range of sensors, and a roof-mounted UAV. As it will mainly operate inside the tunnel, it will not have access to GNSS and needs to rely on other means for navigation.

Figure 19. CART platform for deployment in the tunnel inspection pilot.

For localization and mapping the CART will be equipped with visual and inertial sensors – a 3D LIDAR, a monochrome camera, a set of IMUs, and a system for wireless distance measurements. There are also wheel-odometry sensors available, but this is expected to be inaccurate on its own. It

might, however, still provide information that can aid the navigation system and improve the overall performance. The CART is equipped with a safety LIDAR in front, which will be used for collision avoidance in case of an obstruction in the car lane. In addition, the CART will be equipped with lighting necessary for illuminating the tunnel for navigation purposes.

3.3.1 Localization and Mapping

Figure 20. The localization architecture for the CART platform consists of two primary sub-systems – ROVIOLI, a visual-inertial SLAM component, and LIO-SAM, a lidar-inertial SLAM component with graph optimization for fusing VIO and LIO poses and RTLS and odometry data.

For localization and mapping we mainly rely on two sensors – a 3D LIDAR and a monocular monochrome camera, but we will also support the visual algorithms with inertial measurements from an IMU, and wheel odometry. For the first design iteration we will have two localization systems running in parallel (Figure 20).

In the first localization system, the 3D LIDAR and an IMU will be fused using a tightly coupled algorithm called LIO-SAM1 estimating odometry and generating a 3D point cloud of the scene. As the geometry of the tunnel could be degenerate in some areas, a 3D LIDAR alone might in some cases struggle to provide a robust odometry solution in the direction of the car lanes. The positioning in the upwards and sideways directions however, should be excellent. The main challenge with this approach is that the lidar inertial odometry estimates could be degenerate in the featureless direction, and that it will also not supply localization in a pre-built map. A map created by the LIO-SAM algorithm from a test dataset is shown in Figure 21.

To address these issues, a second localization system is used. This uses a monocular camera, which again is fused with the IMU-data. The primary algorithm used in this system is the ROVIOLI2 algorithm. This will use visual features in the scene to extract information about the motion of the vehicle. These features can be geometrically smaller than what is detectable by the LIDAR, but visible by a regular camera, such as markings on the walls or gravel on the ground. Especially in the

¹ <https://github.com/TixiaoShan/LIO-SAM>

² <https://github.com/ethz-asl/roviol>, <https://github.com/ethz-asl/maplab>

maintenance tunnel, this will be required, as there are no light fixtures or road signs in this tunnel. This solution will generate a second odometry estimate as well as performing localization in the pre-built map providing additional constraints to the pose graph. A snapshot from ROVIOLI from a test dataset is shown in Figure 22.

The information from these two systems is then fused into a system-wide navigation and mapping solution. The relative pose estimates resolved from the camera solution can be added to the pose graph that is maintained in LIO-SAM, to improve the performance in the direction following the car lanes in geometrically degenerate parts of the tunnel. The camera solution will, in addition, provide pose estimates between the pre-built map and the current trajectory and thus both aligning the trajectory to the map and further constraining the pose graph. This can also be fused with wheel-odometry from the CART, but real-world experiments are needed to evaluate the performance of this odometry.

As a redundant system, we are investigating solutions that use wireless communication to estimate the range from the entrance or exit of the tunnel. Here we could place an anchor module at either the entrance, the exit or both the entrance and the exit of the tunnel, and another module at the vehicle. The vehicle module can then transmit a message to the anchor, the anchor can respond after a precisely known time delay, and the distance can be calculated based on the transmission time of the signal. As this system might be prone to reflections inside the tunnel, and requires correctly placing anchors, which must be powered separately from the CART, this will be more complex to use in a finished product. Thus, it is used as a secondary option if the desired accuracy is unobtainable using the previously proposed methods.

Figure 21. Map from LIO-SAM. The color represents the LIDAR intensity.

Figure 22. Screenshot from ROVIO at runtime. The image has been masked to hide reflections and other disturbances.

3.3.2 Motion Planning

The motion planning for the ground robot in the tunnel case is trivial. As no obstacles are expected to be present in front of the vehicle, the CART can base its movement on a set of waypoints which is defined by the car lane it is supposed to operate in, in addition to points of interest provided by the inspector. The slam-based navigation is using standard ROS packages adapted for the CART Ackermann kinematics.

ROS MoveBase is based on a plugin-structured approach, providing an interface for path planning (also known as global planner in the MoveBase framework) and for path tracking (also known as local planner in the MoveBase framework). Grid maps are used to model the environment where the UGV is operating, allowing to add real-time information from the sensor feed about the surrounding obstacles. Typically, ROS MoveBase is used in conjunction with AMCL for localization indoors, and GPS-Based Kalman filter localization for localization outdoors. Obstacle avoidance is left for the planners (both global and local planners). Typically, ROS MoveBase is using a set of configuration files specifying which algorithms are used for each part of the solution, along with the parameters required for the algorithm.

Figure 23. ROS MoveBase navigation structure.

A configuration for MoveBase has been developed that considers the special kinematics of the vehicle, both at the global planner and the local planner.

Although the CART is equipped with a laser scanner for safety, so it will stop if an object is detected, as this is a safe state, no advanced replanning algorithms to avoid obstacles will be implemented. We do not expect that this will often happen, as the tunnels should be clear of debris, and human interaction such as remotely controlling the vehicle, will be required to recover from these situations.

In any case, Search-Based Planning Library (SBPL) has been selected as the path planning algorithm. SBPL is a path planning algorithm based on primitives of movement, where the user can specify the movements the UGV can perform. Primitives are also weighted, favoring certain movements among the others (for example, preferring forward movements that backwards). Primitives have been generated and weighted according to the kinematics. A sample of planning with primitives is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24. SBPL Planning. Left: Set of primitives for a car-like vehicle. Right: Planning with the set of primitives on the left.

Finally, a Pure Pursuit algorithm has been developed as the path tracking algorithm. Pure Pursuit is an algorithm that assumes a constant linear velocity for the UGV and calculates the required angular velocity to reach a look-ahead point in the path that is at most at a look-ahead distance from the UGV.

As the UGV approaches the look-ahead point, the look-ahead point is moved along the path to remain at the look-ahead distance. Our Pure Pursuit algorithm computes steering angle instead of angular velocity. This way, we can assure that the command computed by the algorithm is between the steering limits of the vehicle. We have also added some features to tune the look-ahead distance and provide variable linear velocity, computed according to the current linear velocity and the current look-ahead distance. This way, the UGV starts and ends its movement smoothly, while getting a higher velocity in the middle of the tracking path.

3.3.3 Motion Control

The motion control in the CART robot involves directly the modifications on the off-the-shelf electric cart.

On one side, the throttle is actuated by directly bypassing CanOpen commands coming to the motor controller. This specific motor controller SEVCON is accepting those specific SDO instead of the analog signals once modified for that purpose. A dedicated code for sending such commands and interfacing the ROS robot framework is also put in place. In this way, the robot is able to modify the torque or velocity modes and provide speed or torque references.

On the other hand, a power steering system has been added to the vehicle in order to control the steering. The motor driver has been installed as well, which is using CanOpen commands with a proprietary library from Robotnik. An absolute encoder is providing additional feedback in order to provide an odometry.

Lastly, an ad-hoc hydraulic braking system is put in place, in case some remote stop is triggered.

4. Conclusions

This document presents the beta version of the advanced autonomous functionalities for ground robots and crawlers in the context of the PILOTING project. The methods and algorithms presented here still need to be integrated, tested, and validated. Although some preliminary tests have already been performed for the functionalities developed within T5.2 and T5.4, they need to be thoroughly tested in real experiments in the targeted environments for deployment.

This process will highlight the strong points to keep and the weak points to improve for the final version.

With the solutions defined in this document the development of the autonomous functionalities for ground robots and crawlers can be considered ready to start the next phase, which is their deployment on the target scenarios.

Finally, a final version of this deliverable (D5.4) will be completed by M38, at the end of the second development phase. This final version will take into account the lessons learnt from the first experiments in the inspection assets and will present the final architecture and algorithms used for the autonomous functionalities of the ground and crawler robotic vehicles.